

RELATIVE STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE CELL VOLTAGES AS A MEASURE OF THE STATE-OF-HEALTH OF AGM VRLA BATTERIES

Vladimir Đ. Vukić^{*,1}

Electrical Engineering Institute “Nikola Tesla”, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia¹

Abstract: Ageing of storage batteries leads to a gradual degradation of their characteristics. Particularly sensitive are valve-regulated lead-acid batteries, when the long-term operation at high temperatures may lead to a significant loss of available capacity, or even to a complete failure of the storage battery. Therefore, it is important to define the procedures for determination of the battery state-of-health (SOH) during its operation or planned maintenance.

The paper describes a simple procedure for assessment of the VRLA battery state-of-health. The procedure is based on the monitoring of a cell voltage relative standard deviation in a storage battery chain. In two uninterruptible power supply systems, the state of the batteries was periodically monitored over a period of 12 years, i.e., the nominal exploitation period for these stationary storage batteries. The influence of the exploitation conditions and regular maintenance on battery's state-of-health and service life has been analysed. It has been found that the annual battery cycling, performing the discharge of 80% of the nominal battery capacity, has an indispensable importance for prevention of the premature loss of the VRLA battery capacity. The relative standard deviation of battery cell voltages increases rapidly during the final period of exploitation, simultaneously with spotting of characteristic degradation of the ever increasing number of battery cells. Described phenomenon can be a trustworthy sign for replacement of a worn-out absorbent glass mat VRLA battery.

Key words: *valve-regulated lead acid (VRLA) battery, state-of-health, cell voltage, relative standard deviation, reliability*

РЕЛАТИВНА СТАНДАРДНА ДЕВИЈАЦИЈА НАПОНА ЋЕЛИЈА КАО МЕРА ПОГОНСКОГ СТАЊА ХЕРМЕТИЗОВАНИХ ОЛОВНИХ БАТЕРИЈА

Владимир Ђ. Вукић^{*,1}

Електротехнички институт “Никола Тесла”, Универзитет у Београду, Београд, Србија¹

Кратак садржај: Старењем акумулаторских батерија долази до постепене деградације њихових карактеристика. Посебно су осетљиве херметизоване оловне батерије, код којих, приликом дуготрајног рада на високим температурама, може да дође до значајног пада расположивог капацитета или, чак, потпуног отказа батерије. Због тога је важно да се дефинишу процедуре за одређивање погонског стања батерије приликом редовног рада или планског одржавања.

У раду је приказан једноставан поступак за процену исправности херметизоване оловне батерије. Процедура је заснована на праћењу релативне стандардне девијације напона ћелија у ланцу акумулаторске батерије. У два система непрекидног напајања једносмерном струјом, стање батерија је периодично праћено током периода од 12 година, односно номиналног експлоатационог века ових стационарних акумулатора. Анализиран је утицај

* Corresponding author e-mail: vvukic@ieent.org

услова експлоатације и редовног одржавања батерије на њену исправност и животни век. Утврђено је да годишње циклусирање батерије, са пражњењем 80% номиналног капацитета, има велики значај за спречавање прераног губитка капацитета херметизоване оловне акумулаторске батерије. Релативна стандардна девијација напона ћелија батерије се нагло повећава током завршног периода експлоатације, када се уочава нарушавање својстава све већег броја ћелија. Описана појава може да представља поуздан знак за замену дотрајале херметизоване оловне батерије са микрофибрним апсорбентом електролита.

Кључне речи: *херметизована оловна акумулаторска батерија (VRLA), погонско стање, напон ћелије, релативна стандардна девијација, поузданост,*

1. INTRODUCTION

Storage batteries are the basis of the uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems of power plants and transformer substations [1]. In the case of the mains supply failure, storage batteries should obtain the necessary electrical power for operation of the critical protection and security systems, regardless of its age or exploitation conditions [2]-[4]. Thus, it is very important for battery to be in good condition in the moment of the mains failure, whenever that happened. So, it is important to estimate the state-of-health (SOH) of a battery well before the advent of an emergency condition in a facility [5], [6].

Valve-regulated lead-acid (VRLA) batteries gain increasing application in UPS systems. While the gell (OPzV) storage batteries are more widespread, recently also absorbent-glass mat (AGM) technology finds its way in UPS systems. The AGM VRLA storage batteries are quite simple for maintenance, yet, in the same time, very sensitive to a high ambient temperature and a mode of operation [4],[7],[8]. Thus, in order to avoid a premature battery replacement, it is very important to make a timely assessment of the deterioration of its state-of-health.

In the paper were presented results obtained on “Sunlight” AGM SVT 300 batteries, situated in two direct-current UPS systems, during the period of twelve years (*i.e.*, a nominal service life for such storage batteries). Both battery discharging and charging processes were analysed. Rather than complete algorithm for precise determination of a battery SOH, a simple criterion for a rough SOH estimate was presented, based only on values of battery cells voltage.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

For installation in two uninterruptible power supply systems of one industrial facility, 300 ampere-hour (Ah) valve-regulated lead-acid (VRLA) batteries of type “Sunlight” AGM SVT 300 were selected [7, 8]. Valve-regulated lead-acid batteries of the AGM (*Advanced Glass Mat*) series use a compressed absorption separator made of glass microfibers to minimize the self-discharge and the loss of active material. AGM series batteries do not utilize the boost charge mode, so the battery cell voltage is always maintained in the range 2.25 – 2.3 V [8]. The nominal service life of the AGM SVT batteries is 12 years for ambient temperatures up to 25°C [8].

Two AGM SVT 300 batteries were examined during the year cycling and, hence, during the process of charging the previously deeply discharged batteries. Battery B1 was installed in the uninterruptible power supply system of the industrial facility in February 2006, while battery B2 was installed in the same facility, but at another location, in January 2007. Battery B1 operated until October 2012, when it was replaced with the new battery of the same type and capacity. Battery B2 operated until February 2016. The first battery cycling tests were performed in June 2012 (both on old battery B1 and battery B2), while the following deep battery discharging test were performed on the new B1 battery in March 2017 and January 2018. There were more battery tests in this 12-year period, nevertheless they were performed with the discharge of the minor battery capacity. The

batteries operated with the same type of battery chargers and with nearly the same industrial direct-current loads.

During the discharging, as well as once during the battery charging, voltages on all battery cells were measured every hour. The total voltage at battery terminals was also measured, as well as the battery current (both during charging and discharging). Storage batteries of the 300 Ah rated capacity were discharged by approximately ten-hour-discharge current (30 A) on a variable resistor. Batteries were discharged as long as 80% of the nominal capacity was released [8]. If the voltage of individual cells fell below the threshold of 1.8 V, the discharging process was stopped and the weak cells were excluded from the battery circuit. Weak cells were later returned to the battery circuit prior to the beginning of the charging process. If some of these cells expressed unacceptable voltage during the charging process, and presenting a risk for a battery string breach, a charging process was temporarily interrupted and these weak cells were permanently excluded from the battery line.

During the results analysis mean values of the battery cell voltage were used, as well as the variations of the minimum and maximum battery cell voltages from the average values of the obtained results. Error bars were used for presentation of the minimum and maximum values of the battery cell voltages in a string, in comparison with the mean battery cell voltage. Therefore, error bars were not used in their primary role, as a range of variations of mean values obtained on several batteries of the same type, nor as a representation of the cell voltage variation on the particular cell number among several battery lines. The type of battery cell voltage presentation applied, with error bars marking the minimum and maximum battery cell voltages, in the same battery line, provided clear insight into the influence of particular weak cells, as well as the battery state after exclusion of these weak cells.

The primary value used for detection of the battery reliability was the relative standard deviation of the battery-string cell voltages. Relative standard deviation, s , was calculated according to the following formula [9]:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2}{N}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the observed value (result of measurement of one battery cell voltage), \bar{y}_i : mean value of the results of measurement (mean cell voltage from a battery string), N : total number of observations (number of battery cells in one string; $N = 106$ for old battery B1 and $N = 102$ for battery B2, as well as the new battery B1), i : number of sample (number of one particular battery cell in a string).

As was previously noted, battery discharging leads to increased variations between the cell voltages in one battery line [4]. Also, charging of the previously deeply discharged VRLA battery, particularly some 24 hours after commencing the charging process, leads to violation of the battery cell voltages' uniformity [4, 8]. Therefore, relying on the relative standard deviation of the cell voltages in one battery line enables simple on-line detection of the particular battery cell reliability if a battery monitoring system is installed, tracking all the battery cell voltages. Also, observation of the battery cell voltages relative to standard deviation enables prior detection of the entire battery line degradation and anticipation of the proper moment for the battery replacement.

More details on the performed procedures and examined batteries were provided in the literature [7, 8]

3. RESULTS

Fig. 1.a presented the examination results recorded during the discharge of the B1 battery "Sunlight" AGM SVT 300 after six-and-a-half year exploitation in an industrial uninterruptible power supply system. Fig. 2.a report the results procured during the discharge of the B2 battery, of the same type (AGM SVT 300), but one year less old. The batteries operated with similar loads and numbers of cells, in essentially the same industrial facilities, and with the same 63-ampere thyristor

battery chargers, but in various temperature conditions. For the last two years before the battery cycling, the air-conditioning system in the B1 battery room was inoperable (for the previous four-and-a-half years it had operated correctly). Therefore, the ambient temperature of the B1 battery varied widely during the year, exceeding 25°C continuously for weeks during the summer months [7, 8]. On the other hand, the air conditioning system in the B2 battery room was correct and efficient, keeping the ambient temperature during the year below 25°C for five-and-a-half years of the battery's operation [7, 8].

The discharge of both batteries B1 and B2 was the first battery cycling process performed on these devices during nearly half of their nominal service life operation (twelve years) in the industrial facility. The cycling process included discharging with a 10-hour discharging current (30 A for a 300 Ah battery), followed by the charging process with variable current up to 60 A [8].

Fig. 1.a presents the discharge characteristics of battery B1 with cells no. 93 and 98 excluded from the battery line. The voltage on these two weak cells declined to 1.82 – 1.88 V [8] before their further discharging, after five hours, was cancelled. Fig. 1 is a good illustration of the effect of the battery discharging process on the uniformity of the proper battery cell voltages, increasing the difference between cell voltages as the battery discharging continues.

Therefore, the relative standard deviation is the value that describes the violation of the battery cell voltages' equalization. Line with solid symbols in Fig. 1.b describes the increase of the relative standard deviation of proper battery cell voltages, showing an approximately exponential rise of the battery cell voltage relative standard deviation, from 0.3 % up to 0.7 %, for the eight-hour discharging process. However, if the two weak cells are also included into the analysis (no. 93 and 98), line with hollow symbols (Fig. 1.b) represents the full picture of the battery B1 discharging process. Battery cell no. 98 affected the rise of the cell voltage relative standard deviation up to 1.1 % after five hours of discharging, followed by the value of $s = 0.7 %$, affected by cell no. 93 after six hours of charging (Fig. 3). At the same time, the relative standard deviation on the remaining 103 proper cells in the B1 battery line was approximately 0.4 %, reaching a value of $s = 0.7 %$ only after completion of the eight-hour B1 battery discharge process. Therefore, while the rapid decrease of the weak battery cell voltages down to 1.8 V was a clear signal for interruption of their further discharging, the sharp increase in the battery cell voltage relative standard deviation was a sign of an overall battery line weakness and the presence of weak cells.

Figure 1. a) Change in the battery mean cell voltage and cell voltage extreme values during the battery B1 discharging (without weak cells no. 93 and 98); b) Change in the relative standard deviation of the battery cell voltage during the battery B1 discharging.

In the case of battery B2, exploited with good air-conditioning and an ambient temperature up to 25°C, the characteristics of the 100 battery cells (out of a total of 102) were spotless during the discharge of 80 % of the nominal capacity, as well as during the following charging. From these

two cells (no. 81 and 84) from the battery line only 30 % of the nominal capacity was discharged. It was later noticed that these two battery cells were not from the same batch as the remaining hundred cells! The influence of these two weak cells (for a first three hours) may be clearly perceived in Fig. 2.b – it is a clear illustration of the excellent state of the remaining hundred cells from the B2 battery line. Even immediately after the start of the B2 battery discharging process, the cell voltages of the weak cells (no. 81 and 84) dropped to 1.95 V, and decreased further to below 1.8 V after three hours of discharging [8].

An even better illustration of the bad state-of-health of the weak cells from different production batch are data on variations of the B2 battery cell voltages' relative standard deviation, presented in Fig. 2.b. Cells no. 81 and 84 heavily affected the relative standard deviation, having a value of $s = 0.75\%$ immediately after the beginning of the discharging process and reaching $s_2 = 2.5\%$ after three hours of discharging [8]. Such a heavy influence of weak cells on the cell voltage relative standard deviation may be more explicitly seen if the characteristic with hollow symbols is compared with the solid-symbol one (Fig. 2.b): during the first three hours of discharging, the cell voltage relative standard deviation of the hundred proper cells from the B2 battery line was $s_2 < 0.2\%$ (Fig. 2.b). As may be seen from Fig. 2.b, the B2 battery cell voltage relative standard deviation reached 1.4 % after eight hours of the discharging process. After completion of the discharging process, the two weak cells were returned to the battery line, in order to enable some partial capacity recovery during the subsequent charging.

Figure 2. a) Change in the battery mean cell voltage and cell voltage extreme values during the battery B2 discharging (without weak cells no. 81 and 84); b) Change in the relative standard deviation of the battery cell voltage during the battery B2 discharging.

Fig. 3.a presented data recorded during the charging process of the previously deeply discharged battery B1. Three hours after commencing the battery B1 charging process, battery cell no. 98, which demonstrated discharge of only 50 % of the nominal capacity, had to be disconnected from the battery line. The reason was an enormous rise of the cell voltage, reaching 2.82 V after recovery of some 90 Ah of the discharged capacity. Other cells remained in the battery line after completion of the charging process, yet with more observed weak cells. All the time the ambient temperature was quite high, reaching 30°C. Altogether, the failure of two battery cells (out of the total of 106; no. 4 and 98) was observed during the battery B1 cycling process, followed by a significant characteristic degradation of another four cells (no. 33, 73, 74 and 93) after completion of the eight-hour charging of battery B1. The influence of other four weak cells is well represented in Fig. 3.a, seeing the error bars from the fifth to the eighth hour of the battery charging. There was also an improvement of the battery cell characteristics, manifested through the decrease of the maximum cell voltage following the 72-hour battery charging. For VRLA batteries, prolonged

charging with a slightly higher voltage than the nominal value has a positive effect on equalization of the battery cell voltages [10].

Figure 3. a) Change in the battery mean cell voltage and cell voltage extreme values during the battery B1 charging (without weak cells no. 93 and 98); b) Change in the relative standard deviation of the battery cell voltage during the battery B1 charging.

Battery B1 failed to operate properly soon after the described cycling process, which took part in June 2012. One month later, after partial discharge of the B1 battery, a charging process started with the initial battery current being close to the battery charger limit of 63 A. Unfortunately, the users had still not managed to install the new air-conditioning system, and the charging process occurred in the summer, having as a consequence an ambient temperature in the battery room in the range of 35-40°C. Therefore, thermal runaway occurred among the several weak battery cells, both previously noticed and recently degraded. The weak battery cells, operating in high ambient temperature of 35-40°C and with a high charging current of 60 A, deteriorated within an hour. The thermally affected failure was manifested through an abrupt rise in the battery cell voltage and cracks in the plastic battery cases, affected by the high pressure of the gas in the container. In all, an additional seven cells failed, reducing the number of cells in the battery line to 96. After this occasion, a new and very effective air conditioning system was soon installed and further failures of battery cells ceased. Two months later, a newly manufactured battery of the same type, “Sunlight” AGM SVT 300, was installed to replace the deteriorated B1 battery.

Fig. 4 presents results that describe the charging process of the B2 battery. From the beginning of the battery B2 charging process, weak cells no. 81 and 84 were in the battery line. Since the B2 battery operated in good temperature conditions, with an ambient temperature below 25°C, the thermal losses were much lower than for battery B1. Therefore, battery B2 recharged most of its capacity for seven hours, this being one hour less than for battery B1. The voltage of two weak cells rose much more quickly than that of other cells, reaching more than 2.5 V after one hour of charging. Yet, as the battery B2 charging process continued, the voltages of the weak cells decreased, and were equal to the voltages of other hundred cells after five hours. Nevertheless, since the VRLA batteries operate only in float charge mode, after 24 hours cell voltage equality in the battery line was partially violated and this was not affected by the weak cells no. 81 and 84 (Fig. 4.b). However, this effect was observed long ago [10], and if the VRLA battery operated with a slightly higher voltage, close to the cell voltage limit (e.g. 2.285 V for the permitted cell voltage range of 2.25 – 2.3 V), after seven days of charging, the equalization of the battery cell voltages would be restored again [10].

Data on the battery B2 cell voltage relative standard deviation exceeded 2.5 % in the opening hours of charging, indicated weak cells, but not the bad state of the entire battery line. As was

previously noted, during the battery B2 discharging process only 30% of the nominal capacity of weak cells no. 81 and 84 was released before their voltages reached the deep discharge threshold of 1.8 V. As the cell voltages after several hours of charging equalized with the other hundred cells from the B2 battery line, and the cases of the weak cells did not show any visible mechanical damage, these cells experienced a certain recovery of capacity after several repeated discharges. Therefore, the high relative standard deviation in the initial period of charging may serve rather as a warning than an indication of battery line failure. In this initial phase, the more important procedure should be the detection of the individual cell voltages, paying attention that none of the cells exceeds the maximum value of 2.7 V, or particularly shows and further voltage increase during the remaining part of the battery charging process.

Figure 4. a) Change in the battery mean cell voltage and cell voltage extreme values during the battery B2 charging (without weak cells no. 81 and 84); b) Change in the relative standard deviation of the battery cell voltage during the battery B2 charging.

Fig. 4.b is an excellent example of the good state of the hundred cells from the same production batch in the B2 battery line. The relative standard deviation of the B2 battery good cell voltage was approximately $s_2 = 0.2\%$ for the first seven hours of charging, reaching $s_2 = 1\%$ after the 24-hour charging period. However, this loss of cell voltage equalization was expected [8, 10], as mentioned before.

Battery B2 was in operation until February 2016, and was replaced after exactly nine years of exploitation. Two and a half years after the described deep discharging, performed in June 2012, battery B2 demonstrated significant deterioration of its characteristics. After a brief control, during a regular operation in a float charge mode, it was noticed that cells no. 10 and 84 were in very bad condition and were quickly shorted (voltage on cell no. 10 was very low ($U_{10} = 1.39\text{ V}$), while on the cell no. 84 it was unacceptably high ($U_{84} = 4.7\text{ V}$)). Two weeks later, in February 2015, voltage of another cell, no. 100, sharply deteriorated ($U_{100} = 0.9\text{ V}$). The remaining 99 cells hold out for the next year, until the entire battery string was replaced. Interestingly, weak battery cell no. 81, identified in 2012 as a part of a different manufacturer's batch, was among the acceptable 99 cells, that hold out until the last day – this cell completely recovered after one deep battery discharge. It was not the case with its “sister-cell”, no. 84, as well as with two cells (no. 10 and 100) that were initially identified as good ones.

Fig. 5 unifies results from the most recent examinations of the new battery B1, of type AGM SVT 300. This 102-cell battery was installed in October 2012, as a replacement for the old battery, whose failure was thoroughly described in the preceding text. For the first four years of its operation, new battery B1 operated continuously, without its deep discharge during the periodical annual maintenance. There were periods when battery charger was turned off for several hours or even a day, supplying the accompanying DC load. Nevertheless, there were not attempts to

discharge its full capacity. Thus, in March 2017, after 4½ years of operation, a first deep battery discharge process commenced. Results were not good – two cells reached the deep discharge voltage already after depletion of 60 % of the nominal battery capacity, while the 70 % C_{nom} was discharged from all other 100 cells. Battery operated in good environment, with functioning air-conditioning system and further improved battery charger. Thus, a conclusion may be drawn that lack of annual battery cycling led to the significant decline of its available capacity. Nevertheless, there were not reasons for the battery replacement – even with 60% of capacity, it enabled at least two-day autonomy for the supplied facility.

Figure 5. a) Change in the mean cell voltage and cell voltage extreme values during the new battery B1 discharging; b) Change in the relative standard deviation of the battery cell voltage during the new battery B1 discharging.

The next deep battery discharge was performed nearly a year later. The new B1 battery examination capacity pointed to a significant recovery of its capacity, enabling depletion of 80% of the nominal capacity from all 102 cells. This improvement is clearly visible in Fig. 5.a, particularly when extreme values in the discharge characteristics were compared. Battery cell voltage mean value, recorded in 2017, drop down to approximately 1.81 V after seven hours, while a year later, after the same period, the mean cell voltage was 1.94 V (see Fig. 5.a). Data on the relative standard deviation, presented in Fig. 5.b are even better illustration of the recovery that the VRLA battery experienced after only one deep discharging cycle.

4. DISCUSSION

All the presented results were obtained during the annual battery cycling, mostly based on the analysis of the battery discharge results. The relative standard deviation of the battery cell voltages quickly rises even if only one bad cell was introduced in a battery string. Thus, as may be seen from the previous chapter, as well as from reference [8], bad state of one or two cells may conceal the state of the rest of battery string, until it was excluded from it. Data presented in Figs. 1 and 2 are a good illustration of this statement. Data presented in Fig. 1 were obtained after exclusion of two weak cells (no. 93 and 98) from the battery string during the discharging. In the case of battery B2, also two weak cells (no. 81 and 84) were excluded from the battery string, yet the rest of the battery string (in total 100 cells) had very good SOH.

Data on the battery charging, presented in Figs. 3 and 4, are even better illustration of these two VRLA battery SOH, recorded in the summer of 2012. Regardless of the exclusion of one weak cell from battery B1 string, the real difference between these batteries appeared after five hours of charging. Then the voltage of many cells in B1 string rose up to 2.6 – 2.7 V (Fig. 3), tremendously

rising battery cell voltage RSD (up to $s_{B1} = 3.5\%$). On the other hand, battery B2, except two weak cells, originating from the other batch, demonstrated very low inequality of its cell voltages, leading to the observation of very low RSD during the charging process (approximately $s_{B2} = 0.2\%$).

At last, Fig. 5 is an illustration of possible use of cell voltage RSD curves for estimation of the battery SOH between two annual capacitive tests. While in 2017 the RSD of battery cell voltages had risen quickly already after three hours, the next year significant inequality between cell voltages appeared only after six hours of discharging. Also, after seven hours of discharging, relative standard deviations differed almost double: $s_{BI}^{2017} = 2.4\%$, in comparison with $s_{BI}^{2018} = 1.2\%$. In general, curves presented in Fig. 5.b present a very good illustration of the improvement of a battery state-of-health, perceived during the deep battery discharging with a constant ten-hour current. For a battery with good SOH, values of RSD should be as low as possible, while its sharp increase should commence as late as possible.

During the previous years there were also performed on-line battery tests, during its regular operation. Battery cell voltages were measured in a float charge mode, and also in this case it was possible to estimate battery SOH by calculating an RSD. Yet, there was one problem with this method. It would be necessary to install a battery monitoring system that should measure and archive voltages of each cell all year around. This was not possible with the available battery chargers, and particularly not some twelve years ago. In the case of annual battery maintenance, all battery cell voltages were manually recorded and analysed later. Also, previous presentation points that a thorough insight in a battery SOH demands depletion of a significant capacity, in order of 20 – 50 % of the nominal capacity. Thus, despite the great possible practical implementation of an on-line estimation of a battery SOH, during its normal operation, it should be made only after the basic technical requirements were met for such an analysis.

5. CONCLUSION

Valve-regulated lead acid (VRLA) batteries with absorbent glass mat (AGM) were examined for twelve years in a real industrial environment. The batteries had a regular annual test, yet not always a deep battery discharge was included in the battery maintenance program. Due to AGM VRLA batteries great susceptibility to the high-temperature-caused damage, it was an imperative to estimate the battery state-of-health (SOH), as well as the proper moment for their replacement. Beside the measured values of the battery cell voltages, a basic method was an analysis of the battery cell voltages inequality, i.e., cell voltage relative standard deviation (RSD).

Sharp increase of the battery cell voltage RSD was affected by the existence of weak battery cells, depleted far before the depletion of the nominal cell capacity. During the battery discharge, cell voltage RSD steadily rises, with more expressed rise and higher RSD values for weak battery strings. Data on cell voltages RSD, recorded during the battery charging after the deep battery depletion, gave even more revealing results. In the case when, during the discharge process (with an exception of the obviously failed cells), RSD had moderate increase, when charging process commenced, RSD rose tremendously after five hours, clearly pointing to the battery string with a bad SOH, replacement of which was urgent.

Relative variations of a battery cell voltage RSD, recorded between two annual capacity tests, also gained important use. Battery cell voltage RSD curves shifting upwards, with an increase of both RSD absolute value (s) and its derivative in time (ds/dt), may be used as an early sign of a battery string degradation.

Another important conclusion is that annual deep battery discharging (80% of its nominal capacity) remains an irreplaceable tool for a proper AGM VRLA battery maintenance. While the modern battery test equipment and battery management systems may precisely lead to a quick detection (for several seconds) of weak battery cells and their capacity, regular battery discharging keeps its SOH good and available capacity high. We observed that if the AGM VRLA battery operation without periodical deep battery discharge (as the term “maintenance-free batteries” would

be sometimes wrongly interpreted), after four years their available capacity would decline down to 60-70%. Nevertheless, following annual deep battery discharge may lead to a partial recovery of the battery capacity and, consequently, its SOH.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia under the project TR33020, “The power efficiency improvement of the hydro and thermal power plants in the Electric Power Industry of Serbia using the development of the power electronics technologies and devices for the control and automation”.

REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE Guide for the Selection and Sizing Batteries for Uninterruptible Power Supply Systems, *IEEE Std 1184-1994*, 1994.
- [2] Sun, Y. H., Jou, H. L., Wu J. C., Aging Estimation Method for Lead-Acid Battery, *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, 26 (2011), 1, pp. 264-271
- [3] Pascoe, P. E., Anbuky, A. H., Standby Power System VRLA Battery Reserve Life Estimation Scheme, *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, 26 (2011), 4, pp. 887–895
- [4] Hurley, W. G., Wong, Y. S., Wölfle, W. H., Self-Equalization of Cell Voltages to Prolong the Life of VRLA Batteries in Standby Applications, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 56 (2009), 6, pp. 2115-2120
- [5] Lin, H. T., Liang, T. J., Chen, S. M., Estimation of Battery State of Health Using Probabilistic Neural Network,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 9 (2013), 2, pp. 679-685
- [6] Shahriari M., Farokhi, M., Online State-of-Health Estimation of VRLA Batteries Using State of Charge,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 60 (2013), 1, pp. 191-202
- [7] Vukić, V. Đ., Determination of Regression Functions for the Charging and Discharging Processes of Valve-Regulated Lead-Acid Batteries (in Serbian), *Proceedings, Electrical Engineering Institute “Nikola Tesla”*, 22 (2012), pp. 153-172
- [8] Vukić, V. Đ., Electrical Characteristics of Valve-Regulated Lead-Acid Batteries After Expiry of Half of the Nominal Service Life, *Proceedings, International Conference Power Plants 2012*, Zlatibor, Serbia, October 30 – November 2, 2012, pp. 361-371
- [9] Everitt, B. S., *The Cambridge Dictionary of Statistics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge UK, 2002.
- [10] Lohner, A., Karden, E., DeDoncker, R. W., Charge equalizing and lifetime increasing with a new charging method for VRLA batteries, *Proceedings, 19th Conference INTELEC*, Melbourne, Australia, October 19-23, 1997, pp. 407-411